

THE CLASSIFICATION OF SOCIO-POLITICAL VOCABULARY.

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Abstract: In this article we will talk about the origin of socio political neologisms and their names of the concepts and realities characteristic of different social systems are included in the socio-political lexicon.

Keywords: Socio political vocabulary, socio political terminology, sociolinguistics, special sub system of the vocabulary.

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The study of socio-political lexicon has a great impact on linguistic security. It is becoming an active issue of study in the current situation due to the increased attention to the research of political communication and the processes of communicative activity. Researching the socio-political lexicon, the possibilities of this field and the range of topics, many products being carried out in this field, a number of issues are waiting for their solution. For example, determining the periodic boundary of the development of the political field, providing lexical control of the verbal political field, and determining the thematic boundaries require deeper research.

The specificity of the lexicon in the socio-political content can be seen in the following: on the one hand, its thematic scope is very wide and its boundaries are unclear, it is the terms of the political, economic, trade, jurisprudence, military sphere, and directly proper names and periphrases, full names and abbreviations (abbreviations), etc.; on the other hand, many names, metaphors, even popular nouns used in everyday communication are a certain set of political concepts. The lexicon of socio-political content sometimes includes words that acquire an additional meaning in the political situation during a certain period of time. Due to the use of many words in special situations, the political lexicon expands its terminological and semi-terminological composition.

It is natural to ask the question: to what extent is the relationship between socio-political lexicon and terminology? According to some scholars, socio-political terminology is part of the socio-political lexicon. In our opinion, such a point of view (not understanding the combination of terms and non-terms within the socio-

political lexicon) is probably not quite correct. First of all, as mentioned above, some of the socio-political terminology is used only in special field texts and oral communication of specialists and does not pass into the common language and does not become an element of the socio-political lexicon. Secondly, even units that are elements of socio-political lexicon and socio-political terminology have a different functional description in each of the indicated systems, and this situation is definitely different in their content to a certain extent. Finds the opposite of z. Therefore, strictly speaking, the word humanism does not mean exactly the same thing as a term of ethics, and also as a term widely used, for example, in the mass media. In the current period, the interaction between socio-political terminology and socio-political lexicon is mainly realized as a result of the expansion of the scope of some socio-political terms, and this situation is the same (similar) with respect to socio-political lexicon. it leads to the emergence of elements with a plan of expression (form) and a somewhat changed content plan (meaning). In the 18th and 19th centuries, the interaction of the researched systems mainly went in the opposite direction, that is, the elements of the socio-political lexicon became terms, as a result of which, in this system of terms, the socio-political lexicon, which has all the characteristics of terms, new elements of terminology appeared. The names of the concepts and realities characteristic of different social systems are included in the socio-political lexicon. Depending on the changes that take place in social life, new concepts are constantly emerging. Along with them, new names are created. On the other hand, certain events and words that express them will fall out of use. some are now obsolete). At the same time, the poor, the poor, the middle-class peasant, the supporter of fists, fist farmers, sole proprietors, etc. out of active use.

It is possible to observe that interesting changes are taking place in the socio-political lexicon, which is considered terminology by its origin. On the one hand, it is enriched due to the fact that some of the names that have been in use for a long time become widely used, and on the other hand, new terms that have appeared in the layer of the socio-political lexicon are constantly passing. This process depends on two important factors: firstly, in connection with the increase in the level of general information and political literacy, a wide layer of the population can acquire more complex social concepts and categories and the words that express them; secondly, as a result of one or another events that occur in social life, certain concepts related to social sciences may become especially important. As a result, the words expressing these concepts go beyond the scope of a narrow special communication (such a process can occur in any social situation).

The socio-political layer continues to be the source of many innovations. Innovations are related to the growth trends, social and political movements specific to modern world culture, and the speech situation criteria of the speakers,

such as ethnicity, gender, age, socio-political status. Innovations in this field allowed the introduction of many neologisms. In the process of analyzing the identified political terms and lexemes we used the method of component analysis in which denotative and connotative are blocks of distinguished.

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